

inoculation, tubes were incubated at $26^{\circ} \pm 2$ for 7 days, and the vegetative growth recorded visually in each case (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

All the synthesized compounds were tested for amoebicidal and fungicidal activities *in vitro*.

Compound Nos. 1,3,4,5,7 and 10 show amoebicidal activity at 1 : 1000 dilution. Compounds No. 6 and 9 show slight amoebicidal activity.

Compound Nos. 3,5 and 9 show good fungicidal activity and compound Nos. 2,6 and 8 show slight fungicidal activity.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the Indian Council of Medical Research, New Delhi for providing financial assistance to one of us (R.C.G.).

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Fractionation of Atactic Polymethyl Methacrylate by thin Layer Chromatography

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Manuscript received 22 August 1975, revised 13 June 1978,
accepted 8 September 1978

THE purpose of this study is to utilise TLC to explore the possibility of fractionation¹⁻⁴ of

atactic polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) by selecting suitable solvents and to find out the relations with the rate of flow. Polymers of methyl methacrylate have been prepared by photopolymerisation with ultraviolet light without adding photo-sensitizer in bulk at 40° . The product was fractionated by fractional precipitation using acetone and methanol at room temperature ($23 \pm 2^{\circ}$). The intrinsic viscosity of polymer samples was determined in the acetone at $30 \pm 0.1^{\circ}$, using Ostwald viscometer. The average molecular weights ($\bar{M}_v$) were estimated by using the relation $[\eta] = 6.4 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_v^{0.71}$. Similarly number average molecular weights ($\bar{M}_n$) were calculated by the relation $[\eta] = 7.7 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_n^{0.70}$.

Thin layer chromatography has been done in the glass cylinders using $1\frac{1}{2}'' \times 6''$ and $2'' \times 6''$ plates. Silica gel G (E. Merck) of 0.25 mm thickness was used as the stationary phase. The gel layer was activated by heating at 110° for 1 hr. just before use. 0.3% Solution of the samples were prepared separately in the acetone and each of the 15 samples were charged on the stationary phase. Single solvent as well as binary mixtures of acetone, benzene and chloroform were used as developers. The spots were detected by spraying 1% solution of iodine in methanol or 3% solution of potassium permanganate in sulphuric acid.

Four fractions of narrow molecular weights have been selected for this study. Characterization of these fractions is shown in Table-1. The ratio $\bar{M}_v/\bar{M}_n$ for these fractions is very near to unity which shows the close proximity of molecular chain. Preliminary TLC experiments with good solvents like acetone, benzene and chloroform showed that the spots remained immobile in benzene and chloroform whereas movement has been observed with acetone. In this case, the spot moved upto the solvent front. This seems to indicate that the better solubility is not the criteria for spot's mobility and the results obtained suggest that the binary mixture of acetone-benzene or acetone-chloroform may be a suitable developer for resolution.

TABLE-1 CHARACTERISTICS OF ATACTIC METHYL METHACRYLATE POLYMER

Samples	$\bar{M}_v \times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{M}_v/\bar{M}_n$
PMMA-I	5.40	4.99	1.09
PMMA-II	13.87	13.04	1.06
PMMA-III	15.92	14.87	1.07
PMMA-IV	22.85	21.62	1.05

Binary mixtures of acetone and benzene in different proportions were prepared and subjected for development of PMMA samples. The R_f which was zero when acetone concentration is zero, went up steeply to 0.94 at $V > 0.6$, where V is volume fraction. The steep change in R_f value at $V > 0.6$, suggests that at concentration of acetone $V < 0.6$, benzene dominates in the migration of the spot and as soon as the concentration of acetone reaches $V > 0.6$ an adsorption-desorption mechanism becomes operative.

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The rate of flow of polymeric samples for 1 : 1 acetonebenzene mixture and its relation to molecular weights has been shown in Table-2. It is found that

TABLE-2 RELATION BETWEEN MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND RATE OF FLOW

Samples	Molecular weight ($M_v + 10^{-5}$)	Rate of flow (R_f)
PMMA-I	5.40	0.95
PMMA-II	13.87	0.93
PMMA-III	15.92	0.91
PMMA-IV	22.85	0.87

R_f value depends upon the molecular weight in the adsorption-desorption mechanism. Further work in this field is in progress.

Acknowledgement

We wish to thank Prof. L. P. Agarwal, Chief Organiser for his interest in the work and Mr. S. D. Dhiman and Mr. B. R. Sahu for their help. One of the authors (R.K.J.) thanks National Society for Prevention of Blindness for providing funds.

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